

IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING READING SKILLS**Axmedova Sevinch Botirjon qizi**

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4th stage student**ABSTRACT**

This article explores the importance of integrating technology into reading instruction to enhance the reading skills of young learners. Despite its potential, technology remains an underutilized resource in many reading classrooms. To address this gap, we provide guidance for teachers on incorporating digital tools and multimedia resources into their lessons, creating immersive foreign language environments, and assessing student proficiency levels. By leveraging technology in a targeted and effective way, we aim to improve reading outcomes and support the development of young readers. Our approach emphasizes personalized learning, interactive activities, and data-driven instruction, helping teachers to tailor their teaching to meet the diverse needs of their students.

Key words: Computer-based reading, ICT, reading comprehension, project, teaching reading, student-produced video, Information and Communication Technologyv

INTRODUCTION

Reading plays a crucial role in enhancing cognitive and literacy skills and is taught using various technologies such as computers, tablets, smartphones, educational software, apps, and the internet. These technologies are utilized in diverse ways to improve reading instruction.

Reading is an interactive process that involves the interaction between

readers, text, and contextual factors that influence how readers interpret the text. While the content of the text is often the focus, the interactive nature of reading emphasizes the active role readers play in constructing meaning from the text. This coursework will delve into the concept of reading as an interactive process and explore how it relates to the development of pre-, during-, and post-reading activities.

Understanding the meanings of words is a crucial aspect of learning to read. Increasing vocabulary can be achieved through various simple methods, and technology can make the process even easier.

Computer programs offer a range of options, from basic drills and practice exercises with virtual flashcards to engaging activities like crossword puzzles and word searches. Online dictionaries and encyclopedias can also be valuable resources for vocabulary enhancement. Additionally, virtual word games specifically designed to expand vocabulary are available for students to play. Reading literature and everyday materials, such as newspapers, job information, instruction manuals, and maps, can also contribute to vocabulary development. While most people learn to read in their native language effortlessly, some individuals may require additional support. There are also those who learn to read a second or third language, either with or without prior experience in their first language.

When designing reading instruction, it is important to consider the different types of learners and their specific needs. Research has shown that there is a significant transfer of learning from reading in one language to learning to read in a second language. The principles outlined below are based on extensive research conducted by experts in the field.

Children and adults, whether they are native speakers or learners of a second or foreign language, engage in reading. They consider various aspects of reading crucial when planning and designing lessons and materials. The practical

application is rooted in fundamental principles of learning and research. As previously mentioned, these principles of learning prioritize the learner's perspective. The methods and materials used are influenced by the type of learner and their learning background, especially for children and adults who are learning to read.

METHODS

Technology helps as one of the tools for teachers in non-performing schools to facilitate language learning especially English language during the pandemic for their learners. This is crucial for the school where the majority of the students do not have proper devices to join online learning like Google Meet or Zoom. Teachers have to find ways to vary their teaching methods so the teaching and learning can be carried out during the online lessons. There are a variety of ways that can help English language learners improve their learning skills by utilizing technology. According to Quiz (2021), the scholar described the terms "technology" and "technology integration" in this article, explained how technology is used in language classrooms, reviewed past studies on using technology to improve language learning skills, and made some suggestions for bettering the integration of these technologies to help students improve their learning skills.

In and out of the classroom, technology has become an integral aspect of the educational process. Apparently, almost every language class makes use of technology in the move to deliver meaningful lessons as well as keeping up to date with the latest teaching and learning methods during the pandemic. It is not something new to see that language learning has been supported and advanced using technology. Teachers may use technology to adapt classroom practises,

which enhances the language learning process. ¹

Using current technology in English language teaching is defined as the use of creative strategies, tools, materials, equipment, systems, and tactics that are directly applicable to English language education and contribute to the achievement of the intended goals. Technology is undeniably recognized as an essential educational and supporting tool in numerous teaching and learning contexts. This is especially relevant in English language teaching as it provides several possible opportunities to improve both the quality and delivery of conventional English language pedagogies. It is also best to note that technology is not the only thing that can ensure the success of a particular lesson, but it can help to make the lesson to be more interesting and applicable at the time of conducting the lesson. Teachers are advised not to depend solely on technology in their daily lessons. In this current pandemic situation, a lot of new and unfamiliar methods that relate to technology have been mushrooming in the education system.

Teachers indirectly must familiarize themselves with the concept of using these modern technologies whether they like it or not and they have to remember that it is not simply limited to the use of up-to-date appliances and devices, but rather pupils' achievement is far more important from the presentation of innovative teaching techniques and systems. It is said that students can improve and sharpen their language and skills as they use technology's learning power, according to current pedagogical theories. Students can get their desired results if the teaching and learning of English is carried out in a more appropriate and conducive plus the use of technology especially in this uncertain pandemic situation. As English language teachers, we must use modern technology in our classrooms, particularly considering unprecedented developments in a variety of

¹ www.bing.com. (2022). *Microsoft - Search*. [online] Available at: <https://www.bing.com/ck/a>

fields and disciplines. Teachers should equip themselves with modern and up-to-date technological tools such as the use of applications like Telegram, WhatsApp's, Google Classroom and Google Meet especially now with the current pandemic situation to ensure the smooth running of online classes.

The Internet provides easy, quick, and virtually limitless access to software, applications, and a wide range of social media platforms and materials that can help English students learn more quickly. Teachers are the one who use these applications and teaching strategies. Moreover, all these programs are specifically created to help English teachers succeed while also increasing learner appreciation and proficiency in the English language.

The use of technology in the English language teaching is nothing new. With the current outbreak of the pandemic, using technology is a must. Most online classes have to somehow resort to the use of technology in delivering lessons either through synchronous or asynchronous learning. The issue is how or what are the best method to get the students to learn through online despite the challenges in the form of devices and internet connection.²

The fact that most schools must be closed to stop the spread of the disease, maintaining or achieving good results by the students is another issue that must be investigated. stated that since the modern age is defined by the widespread use of technology, it is unsurprising that technology has made its way into the field of education on a global scale. Now, most educational institutions have incorporated a lot of technology in current and future curricula, and many technological tools and media-based teaching methods have gained prominence because of

² Binti, Z. and Aziz, A. (2021). The Use of Technology in Teaching Reading Comprehension Before and During the Pandemic. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, [online] 11(9), pp.1345–1379. doi:<https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v11-i9/10885>.

demonstrated improved the learning objectives, as compared to traditional teaching methods Reading is a complex process that involves not only decoding and understanding text, but also engaging with it on multiple levels.

The process of reading is interactive, meaning that it involves a dynamic relationship between the reader and the text. As readers engage with a text, they bring their own experiences, knowledge, and perspectives to the reading experience. In turn, the text shapes and influences the reader's understanding and interpretation of it. This interactive process is what makes reading a complex and often rewarding experience.

Good readers tend to use a range of strategies while reading such as making predictions before reading, making connections to personal experiences and knowledge, and engaging in self-monitoring (on-going checks of text comprehension). Teachers can model, teach, and promote the use of these and other effective comprehension strategies to help their students become even more proficient readers.³The need for students to be actively is engaged in the reading process. Teachers can explain key strategies and model the types of actions students can take before, during, and after reading. Students will likely need ongoing feedback to facilitate their proficiency at using comprehension strategies. Explicit instruction in the key elements of a strategy helps students at all grade levels. Developing reading activities involves more than identifying a text that is "at the right level," writing a set of comprehension questions for students to answer after reading, handing out the assignment and sending students away to do it.⁴

A fully-developed reading activity supports students as readers through pre

³ The Joy of Cooking: A Guide to a Balanced Literacy Diet. (2024). *Reading Comprehension Strategies*. .

⁴ Infourok (2020). *Статья: Methods of teaching reading in English lessons*. [online] Инфоурок

reading, while-reading, and post-reading activities. As reading is designed as tasks, keep in mind that complete recall of all the information in a text is an unrealistic expectation even for native speakers.⁵

The advantage side of implementing technology in teaching reading course. Technology is an integral part of almost every aspect of life today. While reading will always be an essential skill, a digital approach makes sense with today's mix of in-class, at-home, and hybrid learning Digital project work can help you connect learners to the books they read, better evaluate their comprehension, and build essential literacy skills like vocabulary, research, and fluency. Here are 5 reasons why integrating technology makes sense for your reading program.⁶

1. Digital learners need to be engaged. According to surveys by Common Sense Media, children today spend an average of 3-9 hours in front of a screen every day.⁷ While some of that may be using an e Reader, much of it is playing games and consuming video. Today's students expect to use technology, but that doesn't have to mean rote practice or simply consuming media.

Make comprehension work engaging by asking students to practice reading and writing in real-world situations. Technology helps by providing powerful tools, like Wixie, that make it easy to create products like those they see in the world around them. Technology also makes it easy to share work with an audience beyond the classroom. Whether they are creating eBooks, comics, or

⁵ Coursehero.com. (2024). Available at: <https://www.coursehero.com/file/p5r7av03/Needs-to-be-supportive-in-order-to-sustain-students-motivation-Prompter-Teacher/> [Accessed 8 Aug. 2024].

⁶ <https://nancyanncreed.com/2022/04/28/case-study-on-zoey/>

⁷ <https://www.thecreativeeducator.com/2023/articles/5-reasons-to-use-technology-in-your-reading-program/>

public service announcements, when someone beyond their teacher views their work, students are motivated!

2. Technology can make informational text as exciting as fiction. Creativity is one of the hardest of the 4Cs to teach, yet innovation is essential to the modern economy. While reading fiction exposes students to an author's creativity, many educators find it harder to work creativity into informational text projects. Push your students to combine the knowledge they are learning with both analytical and creative thinking by changing the product or performance they create as a response to the information they are reading. 3.
3. Technology is especially helpful in supporting English Language Learners to build fluency in a second language, students must develop skills in listening, reading, writing, and speaking.

Language acquisition expert Stephen Kristen suggests that true acquisition is, "an unconscious process when language is used for real communication purposes." We can encourage this process by giving students meaningful and authentic opportunities to both listen and produce language.

Technology helps by making it easy to edit written work, engage with ideas and content in multiple modalities, and practice oral fluency without stress as they record, listen, and rerecord.

4. Standards demand it. New learning standards embed the need to conduct research and to produce and consume media into every aspect of today's curriculum! Standards also share the responsibility for teaching literacy with all disciplines, technology and media literacy should be a seamless part of language arts instruction. The themes, literature, and informational text in your reading program make it easy to connect reading to making.

5. Helps you bridge in-class and at-home learning many sites have already taken advantage of online tools so student can more easily move from an in-

class to an remote learning environment. When students are already familiar learning in a digital approach in-class, the transition to home learning is seamless. Digital tools like Wixie can be used across devices and anywhere students have an Internet connection. Today's creative digital tools don't need to distract students from reading and can help engage your learners more deeply in the literature and informational texts they are reading. It's easy to get started.⁸

You don't have to come up with instruction that combines reading and technology on your own. You can download these guides for unit-specific technology project ideas for grades 1-6 themes like weather, animals, heroes, community, journeys, and discovery.

Make sure students understand the purpose of reading. To get the main idea, receive certain information, understand most or all of the news, enjoy stories, or Decide whether to continue reading. Understanding the purpose of reading helps students. The student answered the question correctly.

On the other hand, in the second part of the research experiment group researchers analyzed studies that applied a series of reading activities divided into Pre, While, and Post reading level. For read phase. Researchers described the purpose and goals of the reading activity. Then brainstorm activities were used to activate prior knowledge as students viewed text titles, captions, images, and text.

RESULTS

⁸ Creative Educator. (2017). *5 reasons to use technology in your reading program*. [online] Available at: <https://www.thecreativeeducator.com/2023/articles/5-reasons-to-use-technology-in-your-reading-program> [Accessed 8 Aug. 2024].

Technology makes teaching reading comprehension easy. For example, students may use an e-reader to read a passage. At the end of the passage, students select an image that represents what just happened in the story. This is a simple way to make reading fun and to increase comprehension with the use of technology. Optical character recognition (OCR) technologies can scan printed visual text. OCR analyzes scanned text, renders it into digital text form and reads it aloud as TTS. This assistance can be handy in the case of printed classroom materials and homework, library materials, handwritten teacher evaluations and grading sometimes students find it difficult to read and understand sentences and words. Understanding reading is not an easy task, but it is fun! Building reading comprehension into students is very important. Helps you understand newspapers, books, stories, or more complex texts. Reading comprehension has many components. And it's important to develop all the elements of your child's reading ability. ⁹

Reading comprehension is one of them. Reading comes naturally to many children, but it is actually a very complex and interactive process. It helps in utilizing various brain functions here are a number of strategies for improving your reading comprehension. Like any skill, this increases the more you practice.

Strategies for improving reading comprehension include:

1. Read regularly: The more you read, the better your reading skills will

⁹ Dance-Schissel, D. (2018). *Technology Used in Reading Instruction*. Study.com. Available at: <https://study.com/academy/lesson/technology-used-in-reading-instruction.html>.

become. Try to read something every day.¹⁰

2. Read different types of texts: Read books, articles, newspapers, websites, and any other type of text you can find. Exposure to a wide range of texts will help you develop different reading skills and strategies.

3. Improve your vocabulary: Learning new words can help you understand texts better. Use a dictionary or an online thesaurus to look up words you don't know.

4. Improve your comprehension: As you read, try to understand what the text is saying. Summarize what you've read to test your understanding.

5. Practice reading speed: Try reading faster by setting a timer for a certain period of time and trying to read as much as you can. However, it's also important to balance speed with comprehension.

6. Take breaks: If you're struggling to read, take a break and come back to the text later. This can help you approach the text with fresh eyes.¹¹

7. Join a reading group: Joining a book club or reading group can help you improve your reading skills and discuss the text with others.

8. Use technology: Online tools, such as speed-reading apps, can help you develop your reading skills.

9. Selecting books: Choose books that are appropriate for your reading age. Then you will be able to read most difficult words without help. When you

¹⁰ Zain ul abideen (2010). *Plagiarism checker | Free Online, Accurate with Percentage*. [online] Plagiarism Checker. Available at: <https://plagiarismdetector.net>.

¹¹ Blazer, P. (2023). *'Mastering the Art of Editing: Effective Strategies for Proofreading Texts'*. [online] Paperblazer.com. Available at: <https://paperblazer.com/mastering-the-art-of-editing-effective-strategies-for-proofreading-texts/> [Accessed 8 Aug. 2024].

can easily understand the meaning of words, move on to the next level book. This way you can improve your vocabulary and reading comprehension.

Games and activities for improve reading skill.

1. Reading Bingo - create a bingo game board with various reading tasks, such as "read outside," "read a book with a red cover," or "read a book that was made into a movie." Give students a certain amount of time to complete their bingo board, and reward those who successfully complete it.

2. Reading Relay - divide students into teams and have each team member run to a designated point where a book is waiting for them to read a page or two. They must run back and tag the next team member, who continues where the previous reader left off.

3. Scavenger Hunt - create clues about different books or genres that lead students around the classroom or school to find and read passages.

4. Character Swap - choose characters from different books and have students write scenes where they interact with each other, highlighting similarities and differences.

5. Predictions - have students predict what they think will happen next in a story, then read and discuss to see if their predictions came true.

6. Reading Buddies - pair up students to take turns reading to each other, allowing for discussion and questions along the way.

7. Book Reviews - have students write or record reviews of books they have read, sharing their thoughts on characters, plot, and theme.

8. Choose Your Own Adventure - create a "Choose Your Own Adventure" story, where students can make decisions for the main character and see the different outcomes.

9. Word Scramble - create a list of words relevant to a book or unit of study and have students unscramble them.

10. Story Starter - provide a sentence or phrase to start a story and have

students continue writing from there .by using educational games in the classroom or homeschool, learning speed reading concepts is kept fresh and enticing. This allows students to get the repetition they need to learn increasingly abstract comprehension concepts as they explore new topics and learn techniques help them understand difficult texts. According to research, using games in teaching can help increase student participation, foster social and emotional learning, and motivate students to take risks.

One study of the popular multiple-choice quiz game cahoots found that it improved students' attitudes toward learning and boosted their academic scores.

Computer programs and related technology can aid in the development of fluency in reading and help to expand vocabulary, allowing students to understand the meaning of words.¹² Reading comprehension benefits from technology in the classroom as students are challenged to find meaning in what they have read .

Many devices include built-in dictionaries and thesauruses, allowing readers to click on any word and explore its definition, synonyms and meaning in context. Key concepts in a text can also have embedded or hyperlinked videos, pictograms and other media that help students understand those concepts.¹³

¹² Dance-Schissel, D. (2018). *Technology Used in Reading Instruction*. Study.com. Available at: <https://study.com/academy/lesson/technology-used-in-reading-instruction.html>.

¹³ michellerisby (2021). *Top Assistive Technology Tools for Teaching Reading Comprehension*. [online] tamiu. Available at: <https://online.tamiu.edu/programs/education/ms-curriculum-instruction/reading-specialization/assistive-technology-for-teaching-reading/>.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of technology in teaching reading courses can have numerous benefits for both teachers and students. Technology can provide interactive and engaging learning experiences, personalized instruction and immediate feedback, which can help students develop their reading skills more effectively. Additionally, technology can provide teachers with tools to assess student progress and adjust instruction accordingly. However, it is important to note that technology should not be seen as a replacement for traditional teaching methods but rather as a supplementary tool. Teachers should still provide direct instruction and facilitate class discussions while using technology to enhance and while using technology to enhance and support the learning process. Furthermore, the implementation of technology in teaching reading courses requires careful planning and consideration. Teachers must ensure that the technology they use is age-appropriate, accessible to all students and aligned with their learning goals. They must also receive adequate training and support to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices.

Overall, the successful implementation of technology in teaching reading courses requires a balanced approach that combines traditional teaching methods with innovative technological tools. When implemented correctly, technology can help students develop their reading skills more effectively and prepare them for success in the digital age.

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